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Engagement Activities Review

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Deliverable Abstract

The Deliverable Engagement Activity Review provides a comprehensive summary of stakeholder engagement management, encompassing strategy development and interactions with organisations, projects, and researchers.

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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
ASREN	Arab States Research and Education Network
CoARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
CoNOSC	Council for National Open Science Coordination
EC	European Commission
EMBL	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC-A	EOSC Association
EOSC Partnership	The European Commission's Co-Programmed European Partnership for EOSC
EOSC Tripartite	EOSC Partnership's Tripartite Governance, involving the EU, the EOSC Association, and the Member States and Associated Countries of the policy sub-group EOSC Steering Board
ERA	European Research Area
ERCIM	European Research Consortium for Informatics and Mathematics
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
HE	Horizon Europe
IAU	International Association of Universities
INFRAEOSC projects	Projects granted under Horizon Europe's INFRAEOSC destination
MO	Mandated Organisation
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
MS	Member State
NOSCI	National Open Science Cloud Initiative
NTE	National Tripartite Event
OA	Opportunity Area
OAEG	Opportunity Area Expert Group
OS	Open Science
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDM	Research Data Management
RI	Research Infrastructure
RPO	Research performing organisation
SRIA	Strategic Research & Innovation Agenda
TF	Task Force

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Executive Summary

Deliverable 2.2 presents a review of stakeholder engagement activities conducted by the EOSC Focus project. The activities are presented in light of the objectives set for the project and key EOSC developments that have occurred during the project period, such as the evolution of the EOSC Federation, the release of the EOSC EU Node, the updates of the multi-annual Strategic Research and the adoption of the proposal for the next European Research Area Policy Agenda (2025–2027) by the Commission.

Over the past three years, EOSC Focus has played a critical role in supporting the EOSC Partnership to raise stakeholder awareness, build trust and ensure commitment to the SRIA goals, which form the basis of the MoU. Regional and national engagement efforts have encouraged active, self-directed, cross-country collaboration, the exchange of best practices, and the addressing of challenges. At a national level, this has included structured dialogue through National Tripartite Events (NTEs), which have directly engaged nearly 4,000 stakeholders from ministries, Research Performing Organisations (RPOs), service providers, research funding bodies and the broader EOSC community.

EOSC Focus facilitated alignment of EOSC-related projects through structured collaboration mechanisms. Collaboration mechanisms, such as Horizon Europe (HE) Groups, Opportunity Area Expert Groups (OAEGs), and the EOSC Winter Schools established innovative formats for knowledge exchange and collaborative problem-solving. These initiatives helped promote cross-project technical developments, synergies, and sustainability through targeted strategies for exploiting project outcomes. The HE Groups, OAEGs, and the Winter Schools have the potential to continue well beyond the EOSC Focus project.

Efforts to engage researchers have primarily targeted umbrella organisations, RPOs, alliances and groups representing researcher communities. These efforts have centred on developing tailored guidance and training resources. For example, the project's Open Science guide for RPOs provides practical frameworks for developing institutional strategies and delivering training, while a MOOC on research data management helps to strengthen the skills of researchers and data support staff. Insights from global Open Science initiatives, including UNESCO's Working Groups and the International Association of Universities (IAU), informed the Open Science Guide produced by EOSC Focus, which emphasises the necessity of flexible, context-sensitive Open Science strategies that can be adapted to diverse institutional contexts, needs and priorities.

Based on indicators such as the EOSC-A membership, the number of participants attending the EOSC Symposia and the increasing number of registrations for the EOSC Forum, it can be concluded that stakeholders' understanding of how EOSC's activities relate to their interests and needs has improved significantly. By keeping stakeholders informed and delivering on its commitments, EOSC-A has fostered strong trust throughout the Focus project. This was achieved through a wide range of targeted actions, including:

- **Monitoring international developments** in Open Science, such as RDA initiatives, UNESCO Open Science Working Groups, and IAU Open Science contributions

- **Showcasing and understanding the ‘what is there and where’** in the countries through the 37 country pages on the EOSC website, all in a scalable format
- **Supporting 33 National Tripartite Events (NTEs)**, stimulating engagement and fostering dialogue between relevant ministries, RPOs, funding agencies and research communities - ultimately reaching almost 4.000 participants
- **Extensive outreach efforts at country and regional level**, including nearly 60 articles and post-NTE reports and 24 interviews with Mandated Organisations
- **Facilitating cross-country dialogue** through regional and peer-to-peer activities, providing a platform for sharing best practices, discussing challenges and identifying opportunities for future cooperation
- **Supporting country-led initiatives** for information exchange
- **Facilitating the visual representation of project results** through the Macro-Roadmap
- **Encouraging cross-project exchanges** via mechanisms such as the HE Groups and the Winter School
- **Documenting project results** and relationships in the EOSC landscape through semi-structured interviews with 24 projects funded under the INFRAEOSC destination
- **Establishing 7 Opportunity Area Expert Groups (OAEs)**, a format that allows for flexibility and continuity beyond the Focus project
- **Facilitating RPO Open Science implementation**, providing guidance documents on strategy and training

1 Introduction

In his widely acclaimed report, Enrico Letta¹ proposed that the European Single Market, based on the free movement of goods, services, capital and people, could be extended by introducing a "fifth freedom". This additional freedom would focus on strengthening research, innovation and education within the single market. The fifth freedom aims to embed the key drivers of research and innovation at the heart of the Single Market, fostering a dynamic knowledge ecosystem to drive economic growth, societal progress and cultural enrichment.

A key pillar of this initiative would be the creation of a European Knowledge Commons, aimed at building strong technological infrastructure, removing barriers to knowledge sharing and fostering public-private partnerships. It would also enhance the mobility of researchers and innovators, promote Open Science, safeguard the autonomy of researchers and address the investment gap in research and innovation.

EOSC aligns with this vision² by providing the necessary research data infrastructure through the [EOSC Federation](#), ensuring FAIR principles and interoperability within secure collaborative environments, and robust data owner control in compliance with GDPR, cybersecurity directives and Data and AI Acts that protect sensitive data while fostering interdisciplinary and cross-border collaboration. EOSC promotes these collaborative platforms that enable coordinated, high-impact research and innovation in line with the EU's strategic priorities, as identified in the recent Letta and Draghi³ reports, as well as the Heitor proposal⁴ for independent management of the next Framework Programme (FP10) for collaborative research funding.

Exposed to the current dynamic global political situation, strategic redefinitions, rapid technological developments and complex governance structures, EOSC thrives on collaboration. In recent years, EOSC's stakeholder engagement activities have facilitated collaboration across disciplines and sectors. By bringing together diverse participants and perspectives, EOSC has successfully reconciled different priorities and objectives, ensuring strong commitment to its goals.

This deliverable focuses particularly on Work Package 2 (WP2) and its engagement efforts with countries, EOSC-related projects, researchers, and RPOs, which constitute almost 50% of the EOSC-A member base, making them the largest group. Given the cross-cutting nature of engagement within EOSC, the Deliverable occasionally refers to key contributions from other EOSC Focus Work Packages.

¹ Letta Report "[Much More Than a Market](#)"

² [Why EOSC is pivotal to European competitiveness](#)

³ Draghi Report: [A competitiveness strategy for Europe](#)

⁴ [Heitor et al. Align, act, accelerate. Research, technology and innovation to boost European competitiveness](#)

2 Summary of EOSC Focus Engagement Activities

The Deliverable's scope is defined in relation to the project's original engagement goals, which are as follows:

- Understanding stakeholder needs and contributions to inform the development of EOSC;
- Developing a coherent engagement strategy applicable across all WPs to ensure efficient coordination and avoid duplication of efforts.
- Supporting the EOSC Partnership in aligning the EOSC's mission and objectives with stakeholder expectations, needs and visions.

The tasks were broken down into **strategy development** (T2.1 - and in collaboration with WP6) and engaging with **organisations** (T2.2), **projects** (T2.3) and **researchers**, particularly with regard to RPOs (T2.4). Since engagement is a cross-cutting activity through all work packages, there will occasionally be references to outputs in other WPs.

All WPs of the EOSC Focus project successfully supported the EOSC Partnership. The activities of EOSC Focus were closely intertwined with those of EOSC-A, which sometimes made it difficult to clearly delineate the actions of the two entities. This report describes the specific contributions of the EOSC Focus project in detail, alongside the corresponding tasks.

2.1 Engagement with the EOSC Partnership

A comprehensive analysis of the stakeholder environment was provided at the beginning of the Focus project in Deliverable 6.1 - *Rolling Engagement and Communication Plan*. It should be noted that for this task the originally defined D2.1 "Rolling Engagement Plan" was merged with D6.1. "Communication and Dissemination Plan" and resulted in the renamed D6.1 - *Rolling Engagement and Communication Plan* shortly after the start of the project. This merging of deliverables was also recorded in the GA Amendment document.

The plan, serving as a formalised **engagement strategy**, included an overview of the different stakeholder groups, identified the overlap and dynamics between them, analysed them relative to the overall objectives of the EOSC Partnership, and designed the most suitable engagement actions. It outlined specific tasks and assigned clear timelines and owners for each task.

At project midterm, Deliverable 2.1 - *Successful engagement enabled and future planning* presented a critical reflection on the engagement activities performed for the different stakeholder groups. Additionally, it included an outlook on future activities for the remaining part of the project.

The Focus project partners systematically collected, produced and delivered stakeholder-relevant content, guided by the Rolling Engagement and Communication Plan as a structured **work plan**. This approach ensured a consolidated basis for strategic decision making and monitoring, while allowing flexibility to adapt and add activities as needed. Some of these additions included:

- Participation in conferences, such as RDA plenaries and the EuroCRIS conference, which were not confirmed at the time of drafting the Rolling Engagement Plan;

- organisation of roundtables with representatives from the Widening Countries and a pilot action for a twinning programme between countries, e.g., between Poland and Bulgaria;
- development of new formats in engaging INFRAEOSC projects;
- responding to requests from the EOSC Board of Directors, such as the creation of Open Science guidance materials tailored for RPOs;
- liaison of emerging Open Science stakeholder groups, such as the European University Alliances.

It should also be noted that important EOSC developments took place during the project period, such as the kick-off of the EOSC Federation build-up phase and the launch of the EOSC EU Node.

2.2 Engagement with Countries

2.2.1 Supporting National Tripartite Events

National Tripartite Events (NTEs) are collaborative initiatives involving representatives from the Steering Board, the European Commission, the EOSC-A, and key national stakeholders such as Mandated Organisations, ministries, RPOs, national funding agencies and the broader EOSC research community. These events involve significant effort both in their organisation and in subsequent activities, creating a collateral "NTE effect" that permeates broadly and deeply through the EOSC community. The documentation generated during the NTE meetings is archived on the eosc.eu Country Pages and is regularly updated as new material is released.

National Tripartite Events

Germany: 24/11/2022

Poland: 25/03/2025

Croatia: 27/03/2025

Czechia: 1-2/06/2023

France: 12/09/2024

Spain: 19/09/2023

Figure 1: Examples of National Tripartite Events within the Focus project period

The discussions for the build-up of the EOSC Federation and the creation of EOSC Nodes required a more direct and high-level liaison with many countries. As one of the three parties that compose the EOSC Tripartite governance, EOSC-A, through its Board of Directors, played a key role not only as a representative of the Association but also as curator and moderator of discussions about the process of the Federation.

Since the start of the project, numerous countries have committed to organising these events, collectively reaching almost 4,000 participants from 28 countries and involving more than 600 high-level experts as moderators, panellists, or speakers, who have shared their knowledge and practical experiences.

An overview of the NTE results confirms that the format achieved three main objectives:

- Reaching out to the community
- Facilitating knowledge exchange
- Promoting strategic alignment

These objectives fostered a dynamic environment for open discussions surrounding the primary national and regional challenges in EOSC development, facilitating conversations with key stakeholders. Recognition and reward of FAIR practices were also mentioned by several Member States as necessary to make Open Science and EOSC a success.

The event structure was adapted to the needs and conditions of each country. Formats ranged from closed sessions to open days where different stakeholders, including researchers from various thematic areas, were brought together. In many cases, organisers opted for hybrid events, which led to a greater number of participants. However, it is crucial not to overlook the value of face-to-face events in terms of interactions and networking effects. In-person gatherings play a pivotal role in building relationships and cultivating a sense of community belonging.

Attendance of EOSC Focus partners, facilitated by T2.2, provided additional support and contributed to help spread the knowledge on the situation and progress of Open Science in a Member State by providing an extra communication channel. The complementary view and additional input thus gathered in NTEs expands and complements the information held by EOSC-A.

Figure 2: "The NTE Effect", Date: 25/04/2025

With collaboration from organisers, a comprehensive collection of nearly 60 **articles** and **post-event reports** has been curated following the participation of T2.2 members in the NTEs. This information is valuable to understand key discussion topics, recognising speaker contributions, exploring illustrative examples, and gaining insight into national plans and actions.

The T2.2 team has prepared and reviewed the reports, through which emerging trends, common challenges, and strategic priorities shaping the future of Open Science have been identified. As Open Science continues to evolve, national strategies are becoming increasingly focused on enhancing research data management and introducing new technologies. They enable the implementation of machine-readable data management plans, and focus on interoperability, and accessibility. Technical and social challenges remain however at the forefront of Open Science development. Strengthening national, regional, or institutional capabilities in support of Open Science can accelerate the uptake of EOSC. At the same time, improved governance and sustainability measures should be explored to create more alignment and efficient data-sharing ecosystems.

2.2.2 Liaison with the Widening Countries

Two roundtables were organised with representatives from Widening Countries in June and November 2023, focusing on national policies, challenges, and strategies related to EOSC. Representatives from 14 countries, and from the EOSC-A, Steering Board members and the European Commission also participated.

First roundtable (June 2023, Poznan, Poland)

Co-hosted by NCN and PSNC, the [event](#) brought together researchers, policymakers, and infrastructure providers to discuss Open Science practices and EOSC-based tools for managing research outputs. Key discussions covered national policy updates, infrastructure development, and the need for a legal and technical environment to support Open Science. A key takeaway was the importance of competency-building and researcher training in managing and sharing research data effectively. Panellists emphasised the necessity of cross-border collaboration, infrastructure support, and the cultural shift required for the successful implementation of Open Science.

Figure 3: “Activities focusing collaboration exchange with Widening Countries”, Date: 10/03/2025

Second roundtable (November 2023, Kraków, Poland)

The [event](#) hosted by NCN allowed the representatives from Bulgaria, Croatia, the Czech Republic, Malta, North Macedonia, Poland, Serbia, Slovakia, and Ukraine to provide updates on their national EOSC readiness. The discussions revealed varying levels of EOSC development, with some countries having advanced strategies and infrastructures, while others faced initial policy development challenges. Major themes included the need for stronger research infrastructures, cross-border collaboration, alignment of national policies with EOSC guidelines, and ensuring sustainable funding. The importance of FAIR principles was widely acknowledged, with continued efforts required to address technical and institutional barriers.

Key Challenges identified and Lessons Learned:

- **Diverse readiness levels** – Countries exhibit different levels of progress, highlighting the need for tailored support and knowledge-sharing.

- **Infrastructure gaps** – Many nations require enhanced digital infrastructure and research data management systems.
- **FAIR implementation** – Adoption remains a priority, but challenges persist in knowledge dissemination and technical expertise.
- **Funding & policy alignment** – Long-term investment and policy coherence with EOSC objectives are critical.

Both roundtables reinforced the relevance of regional and cross border cooperation in maximising synergies and fostering Open Science. While progress varies, the discussions underscored the need for policy support, infrastructure investment, and knowledge exchange to accelerate EOSC development across Widening Countries.

Peer to peer action - Pilot between Poland and Bulgaria

A peer to peer pilot action was developed under the EOSC Focus project to assess the relevance of collaboration and exchange of experiences between countries for EOSC development. In 2024, NCN and the Ministry of Education and Science of Bulgaria (MES) launched a pilot action aimed at facilitating mutual learning and the exchange of EOSC-related experiences. This initiative served as a proof of concept for the effectiveness of such collaborations in advancing EOSC development.

The action was tested as a valuable method for enhancing stakeholder engagement by fostering bilateral or multilateral cooperation, building trust, enabling institutions to learn from each other's best practices, policy frameworks, and implementation strategies.

Through structured interactions, stakeholders could develop a deeper understanding of EOSC-related policies and activities, which promotes alignment and strengthens commitment across national boundaries.

Topics covered in this action included Open Science policies, initiatives, and capacity-building programmes for the research community, as well as engagement strategies. The initiative provided a platform for sharing best practices, discussing challenges, and identifying opportunities for future collaboration. This action highlights the importance of bilateral and multilateral partnerships in advancing the Open Science agenda. Additionally, this pilot action demonstrates the relevance of maintaining regular collaboration to enhance EOSC readiness.

EuroScience Open Forum (EOSF)

On 13 June 2024, Katowice (Poland) hosted the [EuroScience Open Forum \(ESOF\)](#), a major European event about how life changes science that attracted over 3,500 participants and 530 speakers. A highlight of the event was the panel organised by NCN, in collaboration with EOSC Focus, entitled "[Elevating Excellence: Navigating Practical Dimensions of Open Science](#)". This panel brought together 10 distinguished representatives from research funding and research performing organisations to discuss how Open Science can enhance research integrity and excellence. The keynote speakers, Prof. Sabina Leonelli and Prof. Toma Susi, provided invaluable insights into achieving a more inclusive Open Science landscape and quality-focused scientific assessment.

2.2.3 Enhancing National Collaboration Through Regional Hubs

The EOSC Focus project partners have been responsible for coordinating activities across five specific regions: Western Europe (Belnet), Central Europe (TU Graz), Eastern Europe (NCN), Southern Europe (CREAF), and the Nordic countries (NCN). Their primary role has been to monitor the development of EOSC within these regions, support stakeholder engagement, and facilitate the exchange of information and good practices. A brief overview of the regional approach and key lessons learnt is provided below.

Regional Hub West: This hub consists of the following countries: Ireland, the Netherlands, Belgium, Luxembourg, France and the United Kingdom. The level of Open Science development and EOSC implementation overall is quite high, with the Netherlands and France as leading countries. Due to Brexit, the UK was less highlighted during this project. Nonetheless, Jisc (UK’s National Research and Education Network or NREN) stayed involved in the EOSC community and more recently UKRI has also joined the EOSC-Association.

Apart from the fact that Open Science gained importance over the last few years in all countries of Hub West, one of the most important takeaways during this 3-year period is the fact that there was no real cross-pollination between the different countries. There is a growing trend of information sharing among the countries within Hub West. EOSC Focus can take credit for that, by raising awareness within the European community through various channels, such as:

- publishing yearly updates of all country pages in Hub West;
- publishing interviews of the representatives of all the Mandated Organisations;
- helping to organise, attend and inform the EOSC community on the NTEs;
- if present, pinpointing the national structures on Open Science in the countries;
- connecting several times a year with the national Open Science representatives in each country.

In the years ahead, this cross-pollination and information sharing will become even more important. Continued efforts will be necessary to sustain and build upon this progress.

Regional Hub Central: This hub includes seven small-to-medium size countries (Austria, Czech Republic, Croatia, Hungary, Slovakia, Slovenia, and last but not least Switzerland), along with Germany. The different progress between the countries does not hide the fact that, overall, the understanding of Open Science as the “new normal” for (publicly funded) research already prevails in the region. This is proven by the presence of Open Science policies in all eight countries (with some cases, like Croatia, pending approval by the Government), and by the significant investments committed or already under execution in several of them (e.g., Germany or Czech Republic).

Germany has shown its strong support of data sharing by creating its national initiative NFDI. The country has recently been chosen for the first “wave” of EOSC Candidate Nodes. Other countries, including Czech Republic, Croatia, Austria and Switzerland, appear to have in place the know-how and most of the necessary resources, economical or human resources, to follow in the next group of Nodes to be selected later in 2025. The two remaining countries in the Hub, Slovakia and Hungary, are stepping up to get in shape in order to join the Federation at some point in the next few years.

The active engagement of the community is reflected throughout the Hub in the high number of stakeholders attending the many NTEs (over 15) that have taken place during the course of EOSC Focus. The participation of Governments in the events confirms the general support to Open Science and EOSC. Some recurring topics from the interviews with Mandated Organisations in the hub indicate the interests of the countries as well as the “pain points” they perceive for the successful implementation of Open Science:

- All countries understand the benefits of participating in EOSC, both to be part of EU-funded R&D projects and to push national Open Science agendas.
- Open Access is of central importance for researchers.
- Funding, of research in general and of Open Science in particular, remains a key issue.
- Small countries struggle to find the necessary workforce to implement Open Science that points to the need to make careers attractive.

Regional Hub East: This hub is a diverse and evolving regional hub established within the EOSC Focus project. It is composed of a broad network of **nine countries**, including the Baltic states—Latvia, Lithuania, Estonia, and Ukraine, devastated by Russian aggression, and East and South European countries: Romania, Bulgaria, Serbia, and North Macedonia, along with Poland. These countries represent varying stages of implementation of Open Science and EOSC-related policies. Among them, six have established EOSC-A Mandated Organisations, while three (Lithuania, Bulgaria and Serbia) are currently without one. Despite these structural differences, engagement across the region has been active, collaborative, and impactful. The activities of the East Hub have also extended beyond its core members, incorporating neighbouring countries such as Czechia and Slovakia, due to shared geopolitical and regional contexts. Moreover, through established networking ties—particularly those stemming from North Macedonia—the Hub has welcomed the active participation of representatives from Malta and Cyprus.

Leadership by the NCN has been instrumental in driving forward this regional engagement. When NCN established the [EOSC-PL national node](#) and was selected for the [pilot phase of the EOSC Federation](#), it invited regional partners to join this effort. This has reinforced collaboration across Central, Eastern and Southern Europe which has been welcomed already by several partners.

As a result of the collaboration with regional partners, NCN identified a strong demand for common training in RDM. This was seen as critical to enabling deeper engagement of end users, particularly researchers. It served as a rationale for launching specific actions under Task 2.4 to develop a common training in English in the form of a [MOOC](#) (Massive Open Online Course).

Overall, the East Hub has demonstrated that regional cooperation in Open Science is both possible and necessary. The level of engagement across the region—and beyond—has been exceptional. It offers clear evidence that regional cooperation and capacity building should continue to be supported.

Regional Hub South: This hub includes six Member States (Cyprus, Greece, Italy, Malta, Portugal, and Spain), some of which have created synergies in the context of Open Science. Cyprus and Greece belong to National Open Science Cloud Initiatives (NOSCI) in Southeast Europe and participated in the National Initiatives for Open Science in Europe (NI4OS-Europe) project with the aim to be a core contributor to the EOSC service portfolio and commit to EOSC governance, aligned

with the European Research Area⁵ Action No. 1. Greece, Italy, Malta, Portugal, and Spain also participate in the Council for National Open Science Coordination (CoNOSC) to accelerate the implementation of Open Science. Additionally, in the Iberian region, annual IBERGRID conferences have fostered scientific and technological cooperation between Spain and Portugal since 2007, including the EOSC-Synergy project coordinated by IBERGRID.

Engagement activities with EOSC are mainly highlighted by the four Member States (Greece, Italy, Portugal, and Spain) which have nominated a Mandated Organisation of the EOSC-A, in order to facilitate their national activities for Open Science such as NTEs as well as promote open calls for INFRAEOSC projects at the organisation level. Some challenges remain for two other Member States (Cyprus and Malta), which lack their Mandated Organisations to increase the number of EOSC-A Members and INFRAEOSC projects. Nevertheless, key regional challenges in the South Hub share their limited national funding resources dedicated to implementing Open Science practices.

Regional Hub Nordic Countries: This hub covers Finland, Sweden, Denmark and Norway. Iceland was contacted earlier but due to the different development stages of EOSC and Open Science coordination mechanisms in the country, it was eventually not included in the portfolio of countries covered by the EOSC Focus Nordic Hub.

All of the countries in the portfolio are committed to Open Science and have national Open Science strategies and policies in place that give guidance among other things on data management based on the FAIR principles, promotion of Open Science and encourage open access to research data and research results. Over the course of the EOSC Focus project, new bills have been passed and existing guiding documents have been updated in these countries. The RH North has updated the country pages at eosc.eu to reflect the changes and keep the information up-to-date.

The Nordic countries are characterised by a high level of digitalisation and also the research infrastructures and related services are well-developed. The countries are motivated to contribute to the development of EOSC and are keen to follow how it progresses as they simultaneously build collaborative paths towards Open Science at national level.

Interest of the Nordic countries in EOSC is reflected in active participation in INFRAEOSC projects and the EOSC Association members (Finland: 2 members, 3 observers, Sweden: 9 members, 1 MO, Denmark: 1 member, 1 MO; Norway: 6 members, 1 MO).

In addition, the national structures have evolved during the past years. Nowadays, all of the countries have a mechanism in place to gather the national stakeholders together to share information about EOSC and coordinate activities related to EOSC and Open Science at national level. This has strengthened national stakeholder engagement and coordination in the area. Especially for Finland, which has no mandated organisation in the EOSC-A, the national structure is essential from the national coordination point of view.

⁵ Actions are listed in the ERA's [Policy Agenda 2022-2024](#). For reference, please also see the [European Commission's Proposal for ERA Policy Agenda 2025-2027](#)

2.2.4 Showcasing EOSC landscape

Showcasing the EOSC and Open Science (OS) landscape is essential to understanding each country's engagement with EOSC. The EOSC country pages⁶ serve as a key resource in this effort, providing a comprehensive overview of the Open Science landscape in each country. Prepared by the T2.2 members, the 39 [country pages](#) were validated and revised by the Mandated Organisations in the EOSC-A in collaboration with the Steering Board representatives.

While the specific sections may vary slightly between countries, a typical country page includes the following sections:

- **Overview:** A summary of the national involvement in EOSC, highlighting national initiatives, key stakeholders, and the overall commitment to open science principles.
- **Policies:** This section aims to identify the relevant national policies and strategies adopted to support open science and EOSC implementation.
- **Federation activities:** Considering the build-up of the EOSC Federation, this new section describes the national approach to the Federation and the creation of nodes, including information about the national-level coordination mechanisms, resources, and engagement plans.
- **EOSC in Practice:** This section includes practical examples, use cases, and case studies that demonstrate how the research community is implementing EOSC. It also integrates contributions that members and observers from the EOSC-A are making to develop EOSC.
- **Members and Observers:** Information about the country's EOSC-A members or observers, highlighting their roles and contributions to the EOSC ecosystem.
- **People:** This section features profiles of key individuals and stakeholders involved in advancing EOSC initiatives within the country. These may include representatives from mandated organisations, research institutions, government bodies, and other organisations.
- **EU Projects:** This section lists European Union-funded projects in which the country participates, particularly the INFRAEOSC projects.
- **National Events:** Details about past and upcoming events related to EOSC within the country are provided, namely the relevant information about the national tripartite events. These events can include workshops, conferences, and collaborative meetings to promote open science practices and EOSC development.
- **News:** Recent news, articles, and updates on EOSC activities in the country are compiled here.

These sections collectively offer a structured insight into each country's efforts and progress in adopting and promoting open science and EOSC.

⁶ <https://eosc.eu/tripartite-collaboration/#countries>

2.2.5 Perspectives from Mandated Organisations: Key findings from the interviews

To better understand the role of the [Mandated Organisations](#) in various countries and share their perspectives as a "voice of the community", EOSC Focus has carried out interviews with them. These interviews were promoted in the monthly [EOSC-A newsletter](#), which has more than 2500 subscribers.

This [series of interviews](#) was designed to highlight their unique position in linking EOSC-A with the broader community within their respective nations. By showcasing their activities and insights, the interviews conducted by Task 2.2 have helped to identify the connections between each country's Mandated Organisation and the EOSC-A members and observers operating there. Additionally, they have served to increase visibility of the efforts being made towards implementing EOSC at both national and institutional levels.

By March 2025, 24 interviews had been completed, enabling the collection of valuable insights into several key questions shaping EOSC's future. A semi-structured approach was followed, covering up to 22 topics across six main sections: the role of the organisation; motivations for joining EOSC-A; national policies and the ecosystem landscape; strengths and areas for improvement; challenges, obstacles, and barriers; and cases and examples of good practice.

The following sections summarise the main findings in three key areas:

- The extent to which national policies support Open Science (OS) and EOSC;
- The main strengths identified by different countries, alongside areas requiring improvement;
- The challenges that need to be addressed to accelerate EOSC's uptake.

Interviews with Mandated Organisations

The screenshot displays eight interview cards arranged in two rows of four. Each card features the eOSC logo, a title, a photo of the interviewee, their name and title, the organisation's logo, the country, the date, and a brief summary of the interview topic. A blue arrow icon is located at the bottom right of each card.

Country	Interviewee	Date	Topic
Norway	Rasmus Kvaal Wardemann, Senior Adviser for Research Data and Infrastructure	2 May 2025	Developing EOSC in Norway: A Conversation with Rasmus Kvaal Wardemann
Luxembourg	Helena Burg, Head of International Relations	28 March 2025	Driving Open Science forward: Insights from Helena Burg of the Luxembourg National Research Fund
Estonia	Ave Ploomipuu, Information Technology Consultant at University of Tartu's Institute of Computer Science	28 March 2025	Estonia's digital strength in the public sector accelerates Open Science
Portugal	João Mendes Moreira, Director of the Scientific Information Area Unit	19 February 2025	Building a sustainable Open Science infrastructure: Portugal's approach
Latvia	Jānis Grēvins, Director of VPC	31 January 2025	Open Science and the advancement of Latvia's research capabilities on a global scale
Ukraine	Sergiy Svistunov, Head of Department at the Bogolyubov Institute for Theoretical Physics of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine	20 January 2025	Open Science in Ukraine: Resilience and progress amid war
Slovenia	Peter Sterle, Marko Bonač, and Marko Drobňak	19 December 2024	Slovenia set to unlock the benefits of Open Science through the EOSC Federation
Greece	Kostas Koumantaros, Head of Strategy and Proposals Unit, European Infrastructures and Projects Directorate	29 November 2024	Driving Open Science in Greece: Insights from Kostas Koumantaros of GRNET

Figure 4: Screenshot Interviews with Mandated Organisations from eosc.eu website, Date: 09/05/2025

Strengths and areas for improvement

The development of EOSC shows national or institutional strengths and areas requiring improvement across different contexts. One of the main strengths is the existence of well-established policies and funding mechanisms in many regions. Some countries have legislative frameworks that support Open Science and EOSC, ensuring an effective implementation approach.

Dedicated national funding has allowed for the gradual development of research infrastructures and services that align with European initiatives. Additionally, coordination between government bodies, research institutions, and national consortia has been observed in several countries. National secretariats, working groups, and strategic councils in place are crucial in ensuring that Open Science and EOSC efforts align with broader efforts developed at the international level.

Alongside infrastructure, the awareness and engagement with Open Science principles are also increasing. Many countries participate actively in European project consortia through research performing organisations or other institutions. This enables participation in initiatives by EOSC-A, such as the Task Forces or Opportunity Area Expert Groups which demonstrate high commitment. In some cases, historical collaboration in regional projects has helped establish cross-border initiatives for integrating with EOSC.

Despite the progress made so far, many challenges remain as key issues hampering EOSC development:

- Fragmentation and uncoordinated action at European level remain critical, with some countries struggling to align and support their national efforts effectively.
- While some countries have created national structures or coordination mechanisms, others still lack the contextual support to promote collaboration between institutions, leading to a lack of seamless integration with EOSC initiatives.
- Another concern is the long-term planning of funding. Many governments have provided initial financial support, but funding beyond short-term project-based grants remains uncertain.
- Inclusiveness and participatory processes also require attention. Some countries, such as Denmark, Slovakia and Spain, have expressed concerns about the limited representation in EOSC projects and decision-making processes, which may impact their ability to align national priorities with European strategies.
- Similarly, ensuring greater integration of EOSC with national digital transformation efforts remains a work in progress.
- Aligning OS policies with the European Data Spaces and ensuring interoperability across infrastructures will be crucial for long-term success.
- Finally, communication and awareness efforts need to be strengthened. While some countries have made significant progress in engaging stakeholders, others struggle to convey the benefits and opportunities of EOSC to their broader research communities. Many emphasise the need for better outreach strategies.

According to the MO interviewees, while substantial progress has been made, the future success of EOSC will depend on overcoming fragmentation, securing long-term funding, investing in skills development, and ensuring greater alignment between national and European initiatives.

Challenges for the future

Countries face diverse challenges to implement EOSC and Open Science, spanning technical, financial, cultural, and organisational barriers. One pressing issue is the shortage of data scientists, and many countries still face slow implementation processes, which risk creating a barrier for broader adoption. For most MO interviewees, without tangible results and concrete use cases demonstrating the added value of EOSC, engagement from researchers and institutions will remain limited.

Policy fragmentation further exacerbates these challenges. Many countries still lack national Open Science policies, and their implementation is inconsistent even where strategic documents exist. Without effective national coordination mechanisms, aligning local initiatives with EOSC becomes problematic. The absence of financial coordination mechanisms, legal constraints, and issues around data ownership and copyright laws also create barriers to open data sharing.

In several countries, challenges include the lack of integration of EOSC as a priority in the research agenda, a shortage of skilled personnel, and limited national capacity to engage effectively with other stakeholders and EOSC.

The development of EOSC requires addressing the challenges identified, as summarised in Table 1, reinforcing the enablers and strengths that sustain national and institutional capabilities, securing long-term financial sustainability, reforming research evaluation systems, improving stakeholder engagement, and aligning national efforts with European policies. Coordinated efforts to tackle these challenges can help ensure that all countries advance together and play an active role in shaping the future of EOSC.

Category	Challenge
Policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Lack of Open Science (OS) policies in several countries ● No strategic plans for infrastructure development ● Need for policy definition to stay competitive globally ● Lack of appropriate incentives for adoption ● EOSC is not prioritised by policymakers
Support and Funding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Unstable or short-term funding ● Limited capacity for long-term planning beyond individual projects ● Insufficient funding sources to establish EOSC sustainably ● Lack of coordination mechanisms across institutions ● Ministries provide limited support ● No dedicated funding lines for EOSC ● Low involvement in INFRAEOSC projects
Engagement and Outreach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Difficulty in keeping stakeholders engaged ● Challenges in articulating and proving EOSC’s value ● Weak storytelling and showcasing of tangible results ● Gaps between national and EOSC communities ● Misalignment between different stakeholders ● Risk of fragmentation within the ecosystem ● Weak integration of EOSC at the national level

Table 1: Illustrative examples of challenges identified in the MO interviews, Date: 10/03/2025

2.3 Engagement with projects

Projects funded under the INFRAEOSC Destination calls of the Horizon Europe Framework Programme play a central role in fostering the EOSC ecosystem. As part of the EOSC Co-Programmed Partnership, projects contribute to the development of key services, infrastructure components and solutions to implement EOSC. Ensuring coherence, complementarity and alignment between the projects is crucial to maximise their collective impact and lead to promote the realisation of EOSC’s vision.

To address this need, EOSC Focus has established several initiatives and mechanisms to facilitate cross-project collaboration and alignment, seeking to support funded projects, promote knowledge exchange, and identify synergies that can accelerate progress towards shared objectives. The key early development was the preparation and publication of the *Vademecum - A Handbook for Effective*

*Collaboration within the EOSC co-programmed Partnership*⁷ in September 2022 that provides the framework for all subsequent efforts. Sections 2.3.1-2.3.3 describe the collaboration mechanisms put in place, including the HE Groups, interviews with HE EOSC-related projects, the EOSC Macro Roadmap, and the role of the Opportunity Area Expert Groups (OAEs). Sections 2.3.4 and 2.3.5 provide an overview of the annual events, which serve as key touchpoints for promoting exchange, coordination and community building.

2.3.1 Horizon Europe (HE) Groups

The Communication & Engagement, Technology, and EOSC Impact HE Groups were introduced as action resulting from the *Vademecum* to increase the visibility of HE EOSC-related project results through coordinated communication, technological alignment, and impact assessment activities.

HE Communications & Engagement Group: This group, established in late 2022 after the first INFRAEOSC projects coordination meeting (September 2022, Brussels), comprises communication officers of ongoing INFRAEOSC projects and representatives of the EOSC Association. It coordinates communication and stakeholder engagement activities to facilitate information sharing about upcoming and planned events, major communication and stakeholder engagement activities, such as open calls, surveys, testbeds etc. to synchronise efforts and avoid clashes.

Thanks to their involvement in the group, projects have shared knowledge about their objectives and target stakeholders, which has enabled them to spot synergies and opportunities for collaboration, e.g., cross-promotion of activities by other projects who target similar stakeholders. The WG has also provided the EOSC Partnership with the opportunity to emphasise key messages to its members to be shared within the projects (e.g., EOSC consultations). The monthly meetings have also provided projects with the opportunity to clarify questions about the EOSC development (e.g. EOSC EU Node, EOSC Federation).

The group's major achievement is the establishment of the EOSC Forum⁸ as the reference communication platform for the EOSC Community. Projects have taken up the habit of posting their events and other updates on the EOSC Forum, which has since become the main information source for the EOSC Community. This supports EOSC-A communication efforts, as it can browse through the content and get an overview of what is happening in the community and pick highlights for the EOSC Association's newsletter.

EOSC Focus WP6 has led and managed the HE Communication and Engagement WG and facilitated the collaboration in this area. More information including lessons learned is provided in EOSC Focus D6.2 - Final communication, dissemination & exploitation plan⁹.

⁷ <https://zenodo.org/records/11047457>

⁸ <https://forum.eosc.eu/>

⁹ Garavelli, Sara; Pihla Kauranen; Sara Orhanen; Lenka Unge; Anu Märkälä; Freya Goeminne; Stefan Reichmann; Marie Czuray; Bernd Saurugger. (2025). EOSC Focus Deliverable 6.2 - Final communication, dissemination & exploitation plan.

HE Technology Group: This group, supported by T3.2, provides an environment for coordination among EOSC-related projects on technical topics. The group initially encompassed projects funded under the 2021 INFRAEOSC call, along with other relevant projects, and has grown steadily since then, incorporating projects awarded in more recent Horizon Europe calls, counting 72 members as of April 2025.¹⁰

The group serves two main functions: (i) cross-project alignment on technical development (design, architecture, implementation, roadmaps...) to maximise the impact of project outputs and the long-term sustainability of EOSC, and (ii) cross-project cooperation on technical development to create synergies and provide support to face difficulties by learning from each other. The HE Technology Group is formed by the Technical Coordinators of all HE EOSC-related projects (including EOSC Focus as coordinator), and communicates via the EOSC Forum.

The group meets once per month to discuss technical milestones achieved by the projects. In order to streamline the discussions, members are asked to share current technical challenges of their projects. As the most pressing challenge to be tackled, interoperability has been chosen for the meetings during the first half of 2025, which reflects well the aim of the group to seek alignment on the technical development of EOSC. The challenges encountered by projects to implement interoperability as well as potential solutions will be discussed.

HE EOSC Impact Group: The group (HE Impact WG for short) was established in May 2023, with the support of T4.4, to support the projects in planning the sustainability of their Key Exploitable Results (KERs) so they can ultimately maximise the impact generated by their work. This voluntary support measure is meant to help projects fulfil their obligation to produce sustainability plans for their output, according to Art. 16 of their Grant Agreement. The HE Impact Group is present in the EOSC Forum web platform and currently has 59 members, more than doubling from the 24 when it was launched.

The KERs from EOSC-related HE projects were first collected and analysed through a series of meetings, identifying key challenges to their sustainable exploitation. In these discussions it became evident that projects require early-stage guidance in defining clear exploitation pathways that may enhance the KERs' potential for long-term impact.

In response, EOSC Focus Task 4.4 developed the Sustainable Exploitation Planning (SEP) methodology, first introduced at 2024 EOSC Winter School during the session on "Sustainable Exploitation of HE Projects' KERs for Impact". Based on the feedback received then, and building on and expanding on the work contained in *D5.1 - Resourcing Models for EOSC*, the SEP methodology was further refined in the first semester of 2024. The development included work carried out under subcontracting (arranged by WP5), and incorporated interactive testing and piloting exercises within the HE Impact WG. This work, summarised in *D5.2 - EOSC Sustainability Status and Plans/Issues for Future Work*, culminated in a session on sustainability at the coordination meeting with INFRAEOSC projects in June 2024. The session highlighted how uncertainty around the future governance of EOSC and about the EOSC implementation strategy are significant challenges to the sustainability

¹⁰ For more details on the development of the technical collaboration, see EOSC Focus *D3.2 - Report in the form of the half-yearly digest on EOSC technical activities following the ETCC*, <https://zenodo.org/records/10931801>.

of project results, as learned from the first use of the SEP methodology by several projects. These uncertainties hinder the definition of clear destinations for the project results.

With the rapid evolution of the EOSC landscape in the recent months, and the insights from the EOSC Winter School 2025, where sustainability remained a central theme, specific destinations for the projects KERs have begun to emerge, such as the EU Node, the EOSC national and/or thematic Nodes, and the EOSC Handbook. These insights may further inform the SEP development during the follow-up HE project EOSC Gravity.

2.3.2 Interviews with projects and the EOSC Macro Roadmap

The [EOSC Macro-Roadmap](#) for the implementation of EOSC is a continuously updated, interactive catalogue of the results of [Horizon Europe projects](#) developing EOSC, the deliverables of the [EOSC-A Task Forces](#), and selected [in-kind contributions](#) of EOSC-A members. Inputs are tracked over time and categorised according to high-level objectives and the Action Areas of the EOSC Partnership’s [Strategic Research & Innovation Agenda](#). The Macro-Roadmap is a joint effort of EOSC-A, the EOSC-related Horizon Europe projects (facilitated by [EOSC Focus](#)), and the European Commission. Project and other results are added to the Macro-Roadmap on a rolling basis; as of April 2025, EOSC Focus has documented project results and underlying relationships in the EOSC landscape through semi-structured interviews with 24 projects funded under the destination INFRAEOSC (a joint effort between WP2, WP3, and WP6) with relevant members of EOSC-related projects. Through mapping expected project results to the SRIA Action Areas, the resulting EOSC Macro-Roadmap represents how projects contribute to the implementation of EOSC and to fulfilling the objectives of the EOSC Partnership. As of April 2025, the Macro-Roadmap lists 173 contributions by projects and EOSC-A Task Forces. For more information on the EOSC Macro-Roadmap, please refer to section 2.2 of deliverable 6.2 of the EOSC Focus project¹¹.

2.3.3 EOSC Opportunity Area Expert Groups (OAEs)

The EOSC Opportunity Area Expert Groups (OAEs) constitute an important mechanism for collaboration on technical challenges in the context of the Horizon Europe Co-programmed Partnership for EOSC. OAEs began in 2023 as six “Opportunity Areas” for collaboration identified in the high-level Action Areas defined in EOSC’s SRIA.

OAs emerged from clustering project results according to the [SRIA Action Areas](#) based on the initial interviews with projects, based on contributions by the projects to the Macro Roadmap, as well as challenges identified by the HE Technology Group. Another important milestone was the [2023 EC Coordination Meeting with INFRAEOSC projects](#) (cf. section 2.3.4) when the idea for an EOSC Winter School was first conceived. The five foundational OAs were given shape in Q3 2023 when the EOSC Technical Coordinators’ Cockpit Meeting was organised around these five areas at the [2023 EOSC](#)

¹¹ Garavelli, Sara; Pihla Kauranen; Sara Orhanen; Lenka Unge; Anu Märkälä; Freya Goeminne; Stefan Reichmann; Marie Czuray; Bernd Saurugger. (2025). EOSC Focus Deliverable 6.2 - Final communication, dissemination & exploitation plan.

Symposium. The groups were further consolidated during the [first EOSC Winter School](#) (2024, Thessaloniki), and formally established at the [EOSC-GA #8](#), held in Leuven, Belgium, in May 2024, when they were renamed Opportunity Area Expert Groups to emphasise their role in aligning technical developments across the projects. OAEs constitute a mature framework for content-driven collaboration, and have taken up individual, dynamic work plans based on the goals defined in the [first EOSC Winter School report](#), in early 2024.

Purpose: OAEs are the cornerstone of collaboration between technical experts of the community. They are designed to sustain and expand strategic collaboration across the EOSC-related projects to advance the development of EOSC, maximise their impact, and enhance the ability of the community to solve specific challenges through strategic collaboration and co-creation of outputs. Unlike EOSC Association Task Forces, which are an instrument of EOSC-A with a clear work plan and deliverables, the work of OAEs is continuously adapting to meet the evolving needs of the EOSC community, as represented by the successive new projects that start every year as a result of INFRAEOSC calls. OAEs participate in the Coordination meetings organised by the EC, the EOSC Symposium, and the EOSC Winter School. More information on the work of OAEs can be found on the [group websites](#).

Membership: OAEs comprise predominantly technical coordinators and representatives from other projects or initiatives with the relevant expertise, such as members of the EOSC-A Task Forces. Participation is voluntary and facilitated by EOSC Focus. While most founding members of the six original Groups took part in the first EOSC Winter School, membership has become more formal with the creation of a dedicated OAE website and an onboarding process, jointly managed by EOSC-A and EOSC Focus. Since the publication of the OAE website in June 2024, membership has seen a considerable boost across all OAEs. As of March 2025, the groups comprise 228 members, with 40 new expressions of interest received since November 2024:

- [OAE1](#) (PIDs): 24 members
- [OAE2](#) (Metadata, Ontologies, and Interoperability): 38 members
- [OAE3](#) (FAIR Assessment and Alignment): 28 members
- [OAE4](#) (User and Resource Environments): 28 members
- [OAE5](#) (Skills, Training, Rewards, Recognition, and Upscaling): 55 members
- [OAE6](#) (Open Scholarly Communication): 23 members
- [OAE7](#) (Research Software): 36 members

Recent Activities: Following a successful session at the [EOSC Symposium](#) in October 2024, where the progress achieved by all six OAEs was showcased, the remainder of the year was dedicated to planning the [2025 EOSC Winter School](#), starting with the organisation of the programme subcommittees. OAE7 on research software was conceived during the 2024 EOSC Symposium, “to promote all aspects around research software, including metadata, quality, preservation, registries, reproducibility, and recognition”, and formally established in November 2024. The group held its first meeting on 15 January 2025, and was invited to join the 2025 EOSC Winter School.

2.3.4 INFRAEOSC Coordination Meetings hosted by the European Commission

EOSC Focus Task 2.3 has supported EOSC-A and the EC in organising three coordination meetings with HE EOSC-related projects, in 2022, 2023, and 2024. These meetings are held annually, by joint invitation of DG RTD, DG CNECT, and the EC’s Research Executive Agency (REA). Detailed information is provided in Deliverable 6.2, section 2.4¹².

2.3.5 The EOSC Winter School Format

The EOSC Winter School format was conceived to increase collaboration among projects and enable faster progress towards creating the “web of FAIR data and services” for Open Science in Europe.

The [first EOSC Winter School](#) (Thessaloniki, Greece, January 2024) aimed at integrating the outputs of the EOSC-A Task Forces into current or future projects. The event was organised by EOSC-A with the support of EOSC Focus, EOSC-related projects, and local organisers from the RAISE project. The 120 participants included representatives from the projects, EOSC-A Task Force co-chairs, representatives of the EC, and facilitators from EOSC Focus and the EOSC-A Board of Directors.

The event was organised in parallel sessions: one for each of the six Opportunity Areas (now known as OAEGs), and an additional session on sustainable pathways to impact and exploit key results from EC-funded projects. The actions and objectives identified during the School defined the work plans for the Opportunity Areas all through 2024. The full report is available on Zenodo¹³.

The Winter School yielded the following **outcomes and recommendations**:

- EOSC requires an EOSC PID Task Force (TF) or similar mechanism as interim authority for assessing EOSC compliance of new PID services, and to support the development of federated national and regional Scientific Knowledge Graphs and PID Graphs.
- Participants stressed the benefits of establishing an “EOSC Interoperability Board” and collaborations between projects and EOSC-A TFs.
- A common approach in EOSC to metadata and ontologies is needed to increase the impact of results from EOSC-related projects.
- A widespread misconception that FAIR data equals high quality data points to the importance of FAIR metadata for data quality and preservation.
- Regarding Virtual Research Environments (VREs), the alignment of activities (hackathons, creating a starter kit for follow-up projects, exploring the evolution to trusted VREs) seems crucial to tackle known challenges.
- Open Scholarly Communication must be integrated in EOSC.

¹² Garavelli, Sara; Pihla Kauranen; Sara Orhanen; Lenka Unge; Anu Märkälä; Freya Goeminne; Stefan Reichmann; Marie Czuray; Bernd Saurugger. (2025). EOSC Focus Deliverable 6.2 - *Final communication, dissemination & exploitation plan*.

¹³ M. Rey Mazón and I. Hasani-Mavriqi (2024), *Report on the EOSC Winter School 2024*. <https://zenodo.org/records/11165100>.

- The Sustainable Exploitation Planning (SEP) methodology was introduced to help projects plan the exploitation of Key Exploitable Results (KERs).
- One of the key conclusions was that the Winter School resulted in essential collaborations and outcomes, inspiring an appetite for “[more hands-on, collaborative work](#)” and clear demand to repeat it on an annual basis.

The [2025 EOSC Winter School](#) was organised under the motto “[Convergence towards the EOSC Federation: Encouraging collaborative efforts among stakeholders](#)”. The full report¹⁴ is available in the EOSC-A community on Zenodo. While the first Winter School had been organised around the Action Areas defined in the SRIA, the second iteration revolved around the four Strategic Pillars defined in the Multi-Annual Roadmap for 2026-27¹⁵, yielding four thematic tracks:

- Strategic Pillar 1: Sustaining and enhancing the EOSC Federation
- Strategic Pillar 2: Contributing to the web of FAIR data and the uptake of AI
- Strategic Pillar 3: Ensuring research security and sovereignty
- Strategic Pillar 4: Linking with other Common European Data Spaces and beyond

The challenges identified in the Strategic Pillars were used to tailor the discussions, organised in three sessions (one for each of Strategic Pillars 1 and 2, and a joint session for Pillars 3 and 4), resulting in three thematic “blocks”. Each of the sessions was split into parallel “breakout sessions”, organised in groups including participants from the OAEs and the EOSC-A Task Forces, as follows:

- PIDs
- Interoperability in EOSC
- FAIR Assessment and Data Objects
- User and Resource Environments: Trusted VREs and EOSC Federation Model
- Skills and Engagement
- Integrating Open Scholarly Communication within EOSC
- Implementing an interoperable, community-driven vision for research software in EOSC

Planning the Winter School: The programme committee was composed of EOSC-A Board of Directors, EOSC-A Secretariat, EOSC Focus representatives, OAEg co-coordinators, and EOSC-A TF co-chairs; the programme sub-committees were composed of OAEg co-coordinators, TF co-chairs, BoD liaisons, and volunteers from the OAEs.

Breakout sessions: The breakout sessions blended presentations and interactive workshops, and were shaped by the perspectives and groundwork laid by the programme subcommittees. The discussions explored challenges faced in the construction of the EOSC Federation and developed potential follow-up actions based on these discussions.

Plenary sessions: The outcomes of the discussions were presented in plenary meetings at the end of each session, indicating where possible concrete ideas to address the challenges faced at all

¹⁴ S. Reichmann, M. Rey Mazón, I. Hasani-Mavriqi (2025), *Report on the EOSC Winter School 2025* <https://zenodo.org/records/15101262>.

¹⁵ The Strategic Pillars resulted from the consultation carried out by the EOSC Association in the spring of 2024 about the future Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA v2.0). See <https://eosc.eu/sria-mar/>.

three levels (European, national, and institutional) identified in the Strategic Pillars, along with reflections on the next steps and the progress achieved since the 2024 EOSC Winter School.

Sustainability and Impact: The topics of sustainability and impact were given their own thematic track during the first EOSC Winter School; in the second iteration, both were woven into the breakout sessions throughout the event, in asking programme subcommittees to reflect on destinations for their project outputs.

Outcomes:

- EOSC needs a robust governance and an authoritative body for PIDs within its governance.
- To foster engagement, adoption, and long-term impact of the EOSC Federation, harmonised definitions and metadata standards, a shared technical architecture model, common vocabulary, and open communication among stakeholders are crucial.
- Robust metadata, data quality and open source software for AI applications are key, distinguishing between FAIR-for-AI and AI-for-FAIR, underscoring the need for standards to harmonise FAIR and AI practices, along with efforts to integrate all kinds of digital objects within the EOSC Federation.
- Participants acknowledged a lack of high-quality data for training AI models, stressing the importance of defining responsibility and liability for the disclosure of sensitive data.
- There is a need for agreement on a common model for metrics, tests and associated benchmarks across FAIR tools that defines an authority for selecting metrics and community benchmarks.
- More use cases are required to explore the integration and interoperability of Data Spaces and EU Missions with the EOSC Federation.
- The usability of the EOSC EU Node should be assessed through VREs for real use cases, fostering existing communities to promote Open Science practices.

Figure 5: Winter School 2025 Group Picture, Credits: Marcin Plociennik

2.3.6 Some reflections on the collaboration mechanisms

As demonstrated throughout this chapter, the Vademecum has provided a clear framework for engaging with EOSC-related projects. EOSC Focus has successfully conveyed that cross-project collaboration is not only beneficial but necessary to advance the EOSC ecosystem. Projects increasingly recognise the value of staying informed about each other's work and leveraging synergies across initiatives. The success of various collaboration mechanisms (including OAEs, HE Groups, and the EOSC Winter School) highlights the vibrancy of the EOSC community and fosters a shared perception of "one EOSC". Concrete outcomes include the integration of project results into the EOSC Macro-Roadmap, the establishment of processes for structured cross-project collaboration (coordination of HE Groups and OAEs, populating the EOSC Forum), and the creation of the EOSC Winter School as a format to spur new collaborations.

However, the collaborative framework also has limitations. While increased coordination enhances alignment, it also places additional demands on project resources, which are already constrained by their timelines and tasks. There is a need to optimise the balance between coordination efforts and concrete outcomes by streamlining processes, minimising administrative overhead, and enabling more focused, content-driven work between meetings. The voluntary nature of the collaboration framework makes it essential to carefully assess the level of facilitation required to 1) maximise the impact of HE EOSC-related projects, 2) enhance the broader community's ability to solve specific

technical challenges in the development of EOSC, 3) enhance collaboration and integration among HE projects, and 4) to support the EOSC Federation buildup-phase which is moving into high gear in 2025. With the addition of new cohorts of INFRAEOSC projects, this challenge will only intensify, underlining the importance of adapting collaboration mechanisms to support the collaborative spirit of the EOSC Partnership.

2.4 Engagement with researchers and research performing institutions

While the stakeholder group “Research Performing Organisations (RPOs)” was initially considered part of the broader “Researchers” category, it was not explicitly included in *D6.1 - Rolling Engagement and Communication Roadmap*. However, its significance was recognised by the EOSC-A Board of Directors, when the Researcher Engagement & Adoption Task Force (REA TF) was tasked with developing a model to support universities in engaging researchers and fostering the adoption of Open Science. The need to specifically target the RPO group is also evident when looking at the EOSC-A member base: RPOs represent 49% (members and observers) of the community.¹⁶

Additional impetus has come from two other initiatives aimed at institutional decision-makers. The call for new approaches to recognising researchers and the CoARA initiative, and the actions defined in the European Research Area (ERA) – the EC's ambition to create a single, borderless market for research, innovation, and technology across the EU.¹⁷ The RPOs have strategically considered ERA Action 1, 'Enabling open science via sharing and re-use of data, including through the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)'; ERA Action 3, 'Reforming the evaluation system for research, researchers and institutions'; and ERA Action 17, 'Strengthening the strategic capacity of public research organisations'.

In the final months of EOSC Focus, in February 2025, the European Commission adopted its [proposal for a Council Recommendation](#) on the European Research Area Policy Agenda 2025-2027. Regarding Open Science, the document highlights that "structural policies are long-term ERA policies such as open science, research infrastructures, and research careers." The EU remains committed to this priority, particularly by advancing Open Science through data sharing and re-use, including via EOSC.

Notably, a new ERA action - **Equity in Open Science** - has been proposed for the next three years. This underscores the growing importance of communicating Open Science in all its dimensions, explaining the FAIR principles, and providing transparent information about both opportunities and risks. It also reflects Europe's strong commitment to addressing these critical issues.

2.4.1 Supporting Development of Open Science at Institutions

Open Science Guide for RPOs: In response to the EOSC Board of Directors' request, EOSC Focus took action by drafting Open Science guidance materials tailored for RPOs. The resulting OS Guide, consisting of two chapters, one on strategy development, the other one on training, aims to support

¹⁶ Source: EOSC-A memberbase, as of 28 April 2025.

¹⁷ <https://european-research-area.ec.europa.eu/>

RPOs in implementing the principles of Open Science, aligning with European and global Open Science frameworks, and fostering research excellence and innovation. The guides are designed to assist RPOs to foster a sustainable and inclusive Open Science ecosystem within their institutions, thus supporting the European Commission's broader objectives for research excellence, innovation, and collaboration. They serve as resources for institutions seeking to implement Open Science practices effectively and align with the evolving research landscape.

The [Guide on Development of RPO Open Science Strategy](#) is designed as a practical tool for decision-makers to establish a robust Open Science ecosystem within their institutions adapted to different institutional contexts. Its structured yet flexible approach allows RPOs to align their strategies with internal priorities and the broader Open Science landscape. This iterative, dynamic, and adaptable process recognises the diversity of institutional structures, and encourages RPOs to adapt the OS strategy to their organisational culture and goals while ensuring coherence with global Open Science trends, including UNESCO guidelines and EOSC developments and aligned with the objectives of the ERA. The Guide is also informed and aligned with the broader European research policy frameworks, such as the ERA [Policy Agenda 2022-2024](#) and the EC's [Proposal for ERA Policy Agenda 2025-2027](#) that set key actions to strengthen Europe's research ecosystem, emphasising Open Science and EOSC particularly, knowledge circulation, and the development of a digital research infrastructure that supports collaboration and innovation across borders.

The [Guide on Advancing Open Science: RDM & FAIR Training Framework for RPOs](#) addresses the growing need for upskilling across diverse roles within RPOs, ensuring effective engagement with Open Science and FAIR-enabling infrastructures, services and practices. It supports RPOs in addressing training needs by providing a framework for developing targeted training programs. Training needs, naturally, vary widely depending on the various roles within the institution (administration, research support, or scientific personnel), different career stages (students, early-career researchers, senior researchers), and scientific discipline. The guide outlines the best practices for designing and implementing tailored training initiatives, within the specific context of the RPOs and their organisational cultures. The Guide, inter alia, also provides useful references to best practices and implemented courses and data steward networks.

MOOC on Research Data Management: As part of T2.4 and part of drafting the Training section of the OS guide, an available [Online course for RDM](#) in Poland was translated into English. This course integrates theoretical, legal, and practical aspects of RDM, emphasising best practices, recommended tools (including those from EOSC), and the significance of the FAIR principles. It is designed to enhance researchers' RDM skills and equip data stewards with essential competencies. The courses are free of charge, with certification awarded upon successful completion of an exam. They are structured at two levels (basic and intermediate training) for both researchers and data stewards. The English-speaking course will serve both researchers and data managers at a foundation level.

2.4.2 Covering Global Open Science Initiatives

This section describes covering global initiatives and draws on cross-cutting activities with D5.2, and with T5.4 focused on expanding Open Science (OS) collaboration. EOSC Focus teams have

participated in global OS initiatives, also reported in D5.2, supporting EOSC-A and EOSC Focus to engage with international stakeholders and strengthen the EOSC’s visibility in the global OS landscape. These efforts have included participation in key events - such as ASREN/e-Age24, the AustralAsian e-Research Conference, and the organisation of an international panel (Initiatives for data and service federation that can connect local and global practices) in the context of the International Data Week of the 21st plenary meeting of the Research Data Alliance (RDA) in Salzburg, October 2023 ([link](#)).

T2.4 members have also actively sought opportunities to participate in the IAU 2024 International Conference in Tokyo, Japan, that introduced the IAU’s report “Open Science, Challenge for Universities”, as the first deliverable of its Open Science Expert Group ([link](#)).

Figure 6: “Covering global Open Science initiatives”, Date: 06/05/2025

UNESCO Open Science Working Groups¹⁸: As part of T2.4, EOSC Focus closely monitored UNESCO's Open Science activities, particularly the meetings of five OS working groups. Each group targeted key areas critical to implementing the [UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](#), adopted on 23 November 2021.

- The *UNESCO Working Group on Open Science Capacity Building* proposed a structured competency framework based on resources such as [NASA’s Open Science Curriculum](#). It categorised core, technical, and leadership skills to support various roles within the OS ecosystem, while the group’s discussions identified integration challenges and the need for educator training.

¹⁸ <https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science/implementation>

- The *UNESCO Working Group on Open Science Monitoring Framework* shared presented insights from the [CERN-NASA Evidence-Based Policy for Open Science](#), emphasising the importance of national OS reporting, policy monitoring, and KPI development.
- The *UNESCO Working Group on Open Science Funding and Incentives* released the [Guide for Funding Open Science](#), outlining funding design principles and key cost areas—such as research, publishing, data, and infrastructure development.
- The *UNESCO Working Group on Open Science Policies and Policy Instruments* explored the impact of OS policy propagation, highlighted successful institutional policies (e.g. [EMBL](#), [CERN](#)), and discussed tools for monitoring OS uptake, such as [OpenAIRE](#).
- The *UNESCO Working Group on Open Science Infrastructures* explored the intersection of Open Science and AI, examining benefits and challenges, while highlighting a need for stakeholder collaborative contributions and approach to AI's transformative impact on research.

EOSC Focus participated in the working groups' final meetings and published a series of articles sharing the findings on the EOSC Forum. The findings and recommendations of these UNESCO Working Groups informed the development of the [Open Science Guide for RPOs](#), described earlier in this report, which offers a structured yet flexible approach to develop effective, context-sensitive OS strategies aligned with the RPOs' internal priorities and evolving global developments and best practices.

2.4.3 Engagement with Umbrella Organisations

While EOSC-A led calls with the university associations LERU, CESAER, The Guild and EUA, T2.4 took part in the 2004 International Conference of the **International Association of Universities** (IAU)¹⁹. This introduced the IAU's report [“Open Science, Challenge for Universities”](#). The report emphasised the crucial role of universities as custodians of publicly funded research and knowledge creation hubs in driving the Open Science movement. It also called for urgent reforms in university rankings, assessment systems and scientific publishing.

T2.4 engaged with the report's findings and produced a [video interview](#) with Trine Jensen,²⁰ who leads the work on the strategic priority of higher education and digital transformation at the IAU. She outlined how universities can respond to digitalisation and global challenges. The discussion highlighted the need to raise awareness among higher education leaders and policymakers about institutional changes required for Open Science, and the importance of universities leading by example. Topics included AI's impact on education and research, collaboration for Open Science adoption, and the lack of a unified institutional voice in global debates. Key priorities discussed were:

- Scientific integrity: Ensuring scrutiny, replication, and fraud prevention.
- Open collaboration: Enhancing data sharing and embedding Open Science in education.
- Societal engagement: Promoting transdisciplinary collaboration to boost knowledge uptake and defend science.

¹⁹ <https://www.iau-aiu.net/>

²⁰ Vins, D. (2024, November 27). Interview with Trine Jensen, IAU (1.0.0). TU Wien. <https://doi.org/10.48436/bx76n-q1335>

- International community building: Uniting universities to address global challenges collectively.

Insights from the IAU report and conference helped shape the Open Science Guide for RPOs. T2.4 identified a key gap: global OS recommendations often target national governments, practical guidance for RPOs remains limited.

University Alliances: Open Science is gradually being integrated into European University Alliances. In June 2024, T2.4 organised a virtual round table with the EULiST Alliance²¹, inviting the president of EOSC-A to introduce EOSC to Alliance partners and encourage membership. As a key takeaway from this event, EULiST proposed engaging with relevant transorganisational and national bodies, such as Mandated Organisations or university associations like the EUA. TU Graz - partner in WP2 and member in the Alliance Unite!²² - furthermore reported that in Unite!, Open Science has already been on the agenda for the last few years.

University Alliances are collaborating through the FOREU4ALL²³ community of practice, comprising 64 European University alliances and other higher education stakeholders. The initiative aims to strengthen cooperation through peer learning, knowledge exchange, and dissemination of best practices. In February 2025, a call for topical groups was issued, including one dedicated to “Open Science.”

Researchers’ Network: Members of T2.4 participated in the meetings of the European Research Consortium for Informatics and Mathematics (ERCIM) ([link](#)), springs and autumns from 2022-2025, sharing EOSC developments with ERCIM Partner Organisations, [publication](#) in the ERCIM News.

2.4.4 Some reflections on researcher and RPO engagement

The Focus strategy of engaging **key intermediaries** is reinforced by findings from EOSC-A Task Forces (TFs). Four of the original TFs addressed RPO-relevant topics, culminating in the joint publication [Fostering Open Science in Europe: Engagement Strategies from EOSC's Task Forces on Research Careers and Curricula](#)²⁴ which highlights the role of intermediaries such as Research Infrastructures (RIs), Science Clusters, libraries, universities, and associations. This aligns with T2.4’s approach to researcher engagement via intermediaries like RPOs and alliances. The report also stresses that a one-size-fits-all model is not feasible, as each country faces distinct needs, challenges, and opportunities - an observation also noted by T2.2. Instead, it recommends a mix of general actions and tailored strategies suited to specific national or institutional contexts.

²¹ <https://eulist.university/>

²² <https://www.unite-university.eu/>

²³ <https://education.ec.europa.eu/news/community-of-practice-for-european-universities-alliances-and-beyond>

²⁴ Fostering Open Science in Europe, DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10925394

The impossibility of a one-size-fits-all approach also became very clear during the preparation of the Open Science Guide. Multiple iterations and feedback cycles have shown that groups such as RPO management, support staff, and researchers do require distinct types of input and materials. Thus, with the OS Guide, T2.4 focused particularly on the management level, trying to implement feedback such as *'you have to convince me first, for details I will go and involve dedicated staff'*. For the Open Science Strategy document, it was also clear that strategy and policy approaches operate on different levels, and that the decision-maker environment will always depend on European and national strategic objectives, such as ERA actions.

Future challenges and opportunities

Earlier concerns about lack of tangible benefits are beginning to be addressed. Stakeholders are increasingly able to recognise and appreciate the value and impact of EOSC. The emerging EOSC Federation will offer many opportunities to engage both RPOs and researchers. RPOs will be particularly interested in understanding what it means to offer their services within the Federation, while researchers may be engaged by using the services offered through the EOSC EU Node and further Nodes. Engagement and outreach efforts will focus on highlighting tangible results, added value and concrete benefits. It is likely to remain a challenge to clearly demonstrate to RPOs and researchers how EOSC offers benefits beyond the services and processes already available.

The interviews with the Mandated Organisations, organised by T2.2, also provided insights into RPOs and researchers. Many countries have invested in national repositories, high-performance computing centres and networks of data stewards. However, fragmentation and a lack of coordination at the European level remain significant barriers. Overall, infrastructure development has advanced, yet alignment with the EOSC remains difficult, especially where dedicated funding for EOSC-related activities is lacking. Some governments provide support without additional financial backing, which leaves national infrastructures underdeveloped and integration efforts at risk.

A shortage of skilled professionals further hampers progress. Without trained data stewards and RDM experts, the impact of Open Science initiatives is weakened, prompting calls for accelerated capacity building and improved incentives. Additionally, academic recognition and reward systems do not yet sufficiently support Open Science practices.

Cultural change is essential to ensure acceptance among researchers and remains a fundamental requirement for EOSC. Many researchers still view data as personal property rather than a shared resource. Changing this mindset requires systemic reforms to the way research data is valued. Furthermore, the skills gap between researchers and service providers hinders the adoption of Open Science practices. Supporting staff in using digital tools and data management systems, and encouraging the future adoption of EOSC services, remain priorities, however—current efforts are insufficient.

3 Conclusion

The EOSC Focus project has played a key role in supporting the EOSC Partnership through sustained stakeholder engagement and structured collaboration, thereby fostering alignment, building trust and laying the foundations for a more cohesive European Open Science ecosystem. As the EOSC Federation continues to evolve, it will remain important to foster cross-fertilisation and information sharing to maintain and build on this progress.

Key outcomes and future priorities include:

- Structured engagement through a Rolling Engagement and Communication Plan, involving various stakeholder groups, with clear timelines and assigned owners for each task. While this approach provides a solid foundation for strategic decision-making and monitoring, it must also allow for flexibility when necessary.
- Strengthened alignment of national stakeholders through NTEs and Widening Countries activities. Notably, there is a growing trend towards information sharing and structured regional initiatives, both evident across and facilitated by coordinating activities in five specific regions across Europe.
- Improved visibility of progress through tools such as the Macro-Roadmap, which showcases project results, and the EOSC Country Pages, which detail Open Science and EOSC developments in each country. The Macro-Roadmap was facilitated through semi-structured interviews, enabling the documentation of INFRAEOSC project outcomes and their mapping to the SRIA Action Areas.
- Interviews with Mandated Organisations in different countries have provided a deeper understanding of their role and perspectives as the “voice of the community”. These interviews have also helped to identify links between national stakeholders and to gather valuable insights into key issues shaping the future of EOSC.
- Established structures and platforms for collaboration, such as the OAEGs, HE Groups, and the EOSC Winter Schools have enabled technical and strategic co-creation. However, while enhanced coordination improves alignment, it also places additional demands on already limited project resources. As new INFRAEOSC projects join the ecosystem, managing complexity and ensuring coherence across initiatives will become even more critical.
- Targeted engagement with key intermediaries, including RPOs and representatives of the research communities, was a cornerstone of the Focus project. Looking ahead, the evolving EOSC Federation will offer new opportunities to engage both RPOs and researchers. RPOs will seek clarity on what it means to offer their services within the Federation, while researchers may be drawn in by the services provided through the EOSC EU Node and future Nodes. The added value of EOSC, i.e., its offerings beyond already existing services, needs to be clearly and consistently communicated to researchers, service providers and RPOs. Additionally, there is a growing need for upskilling across various roles within the institutions. Competencies in data management, FAIR and AI skills are increasingly important to establish a blueprint ensuring that data meets the rigorous standards required for both human and machine use.

- Strategic positioning within EU policy, particularly through alignment with the ERA Policy Agenda 2025–2027, with a continued emphasis on FAIR data, responsible AI, and digital sovereignty. To manage the growing complexity of the ecosystem and ensure the alignment of national initiatives, such as repositories, high-performance computing infrastructures, and data management networks, with the EOSC Federation, sustained investment and coordination are required. This will foster interoperability and guarantee long-term sustainability.

The EOSC Focus project leaves a strong foundation and a vibrant community from which the next phase of EOSC can grow. Realising the vision of “one EOSC” will depend on clear communication of added value, continued policy and institutional engagement, and a researcher-centric approach to Open Science implementation across Europe.

Annexes

Appendix A: NTEs

Title	Date	Place
National Tripartite Event Austria	23/05/2022	Vienna, Austria
National Tripartite Event Ireland	28/09/2022	Dublin, Ireland
Tripartite Event Nordic & Baltic Countries	04/10/2022	Tallinn, Estonia
National Tripartite Event Greece	06/10/2022	Athens, Greece
Spain and Portugal EOSC Tripartite Event	10/10/2022	Faro, Portugal
National Tripartite Event Slovenia	11/10/2022	Ljubljana, Slovenia
National Tripartite Event Poland	24-26/10/2022	Krakow, Poland
National Tripartite Event Georgia	02-04/11/2022	Tbilisi, Georgia
National Tripartite Event Germany	24/11/2022	Karlsruhe, Germany
EOSC National Event Switzerland	08/03/2023	Bern, Switzerland
National Tripartite Event Hungary	23/03/2023	Budapest, Hungary
National Tripartite Event Bulgaria	28/03/2023	Sofia, Bulgaria
National Tripartite Event Croatia	30/03/2023	Zagreb, Croatia
National Tripartite Event Netherlands	11/04/2023	Utrecht, Netherlands
National Tripartite Event Slovakia	31/05/2023	Bratislava, Slovakia
National Tripartite Event Czech Republic	01-02/06/2023	Prague, Czech Republic
National Tripartite Event Italy	05/06/2023	Rome, Italy
National Tripartite Event France	13-14/06/2023	Montpellier, France
National Tripartite Event Spain	19/09/2023	Madrid, Spain
National Tripartite Event Ireland	03/11/2023	Dublin, Ireland
National Tripartite Event: Poland	06-07/11/2023	Krakow, Poland
National Tripartite Event: Slovenia	14/11/2023	Ljubljana, Slovenia

National Tripartite Event: Belgium	16/04/2024	Brussels, Belgium
National Tripartite Event: Croatia	19/04/2024	Zagreb, Croatia
National Tripartite Event: Netherlands	22/05/2024	Utrecht, The Netherlands
National Tripartite Event: France	12-13/09/2024	Paris, France
National Tripartite Event: Spain	24/09/2024	Online
National Tripartite Event: Hungary	07/11/2024	Budapest, Hungary
National Tripartite Event: Slovenia	03-04/11/2024	Ljubljana, Slovenia
National Tripartite Event: Greece	10/12/2024	Athens, Greece
National Tripartite Event: Poland	25/03/2025	Krakow, Poland
National Tripartite Event: Croatia	27/03/2025	Zagreb, Croatia

Appendix B: Targeted Countries by the NTE

Country	Date	Place
Austria	23/05/2022	Vienna
Belgium	16/04/2024	Brussels
Bulgaria	28/03/2023	Sofia
Croatia	30/03/2023 19/04/2024 27/03/2025	Zagreb
Czech Republic	01-02/06/2023	Prague
Denmark	04/10/2022	Tallinn
Estonia	04/10/2022	Tallinn
Faroe Islands	04/10/2022	Tallinn
Finland	04/10/2022	Tallinn

France	13-14/06/2023	Montpellier
France	12-13/09/2024	Paris
Georgia	02-04/11/2022	Tbilisi
Germany	24/11/2022	Karlsruhe
Greece	06/10/2022 10/12/2024	Athens
Hungary	23/03/2023 07/11/2024	Budapest
Iceland	04/10/2022	Tallinn
Ireland	28.09.2022 03/11/2023	Dublin
Italy	05/06/2023	Rome
Latvia	04/10/2022	Tallinn
Lithuania	04/10/2022	Tallinn
Norway	04/10/2022	Tallinn
Poland	24-26/10/2022 06-07/11/2023 25/03/2025	Krakow
Portugal	10/10/2022	Faro
Slovakia	31/05/2023	Bratislava
Slovenia	11/10/2022 14/11/2023 02/12/2024	Ljubljana

Spain	10/10/2022 19/09/2023 24/09/2024	Faro Madrid Online
Sweden	04/10/2022	Tallinn
Switzerland	08/03/2023	Bern
The Netherlands	11/04/2023 22/05/2024	Utrecht

Appendix C: Country Pages

Country	Regional Hub
Austria	RH Central
Belgium	RH West
Bulgaria	RH East
Croatia	RH Central
Cyprus	RH South
Czech Republic	RH Central
Denmark	RH Nordics
Estonia	RH East
Finland	RH Nordics
Faroe Islands	RH Nordics
France	RH West
Georgia	RH East
Germany	RH Central
Greece	RH South

Hungary	RH Central
Iceland	RH Nordics
Ireland	RH West
Italy	RH South
Latvia	RH East
Lithuania	RH East
Luxembourg	RH West
Malta	RH South
Netherlands	RH West
North Macedonia	RH Central
Norway	RH Nordics
Poland	RH East
Portugal	RH South
Romania	RH East
Slovakia	RH Central
Slovenia	RH Central
Spain	RH South
Sweden	RH Nordics
Switzerland	RH Central
Ukraine	RH East
Turkey	RH South
Serbia	RH East
Armenia	Not covered by any RH
Bosnia-Herzegovina	Not covered by any RH

Appendix D: MO Interviews

Title	Interviewee	MO Name	Country	Regional Hub
Interview with Chris De Loof of Belnet, Belgium’s EOSC-A Mandated Organisation	Chris De Loof	Belnet	Belgium	RH West
Interview with Luděk Matyska of CESNET, EOSC-A Czech Mandated Organisation	Luděk Matyska	CESNET	Czech Republic	RH Central
Interlinking EOSC and the Danish national agenda: the Danish e-Infrastructure Consortium	Anne Sofie Fink Anders Conrad	DeiC	Denmark	RH Nordics
Ready for EOSC: an interview with Paolo Budroni of EOSC Support Office Austria	Paolo Budroni	ACONET Verein	Austria	RH Central
SURF, The Netherlands, and EOSC development	Laurents Sesink	SURF	The Netherlands	RH West
Believing in Open Science: Interview with Isabel Diaz of CSIC	Isabel Diaz	CSIC	Spain	RH South
Challenges and opportunities for EOSC development in Germany: A conversation with York Sure-Vetter	York Sure-Vetter	NFDI	Germany	RH Central

Title	Interviewee	MO Name	Country	Regional Hub
Boosting OS uptake through collaboration: Interview with Sumithra Velupillai of the Swedish Research Council	Sumithra Velupillai	Swedish Research Council	Sweden	RH Nordics
Building the ‘people ecosystem’ in Ireland: Interview with Roberto Sabatino of HEAnet	Roberto Sabatino	Heanet	Ireland	RH West
Laying the groundwork for Open Science in Slovakia: Interview with Anna Krivjanská from CVTI SR	Anna Krivjanská	CVTI SR	Slovakia	RH Central
Building a digital infrastructure to advance Open Science in Croatia: Interview with Ivan Marić of SRCE	Ivan Marić	SRCE	Croatia	RH Central
Focusing on the human dimension of Open Science: Interview with Mauro Campanella of Consortium GARR	Mauro Campanella	Consortium GARR	Italy	RH South
Empowering the EOSC community through Switzerland’s direct democracy: Interview with Annika Glauner and Thomas Schulthess	Annika Glauner Thomas Schulthess	ETH Zürich	Switzerland	RH Central

Title	Interviewee	MO Name	Country	Regional Hub
Working together outside national silos to make Open Science the new normal: Interview with Aneta Pazik-Aybar of NCN	Aneta Pazik-Aybar	NCN	Poland	RH East
Exploring France’s long-standing commitment to Open Science: Interview with Laurent Romary of Inria	Laurent Romary	Inria	France	RH West
Together we are stronger: Anastas Mishev on national structures in North Macedonia, regional collaboration and EOSC’s node-based architecture	Anastas Mishev	University Ss Cyril and Methodius in Skopje, Faculty of Computer Science and Engineering	North Macedonia	RH East
Romania’s strategic role in advancing Open Science and research data management: Insights from Victor Vevera and Dragoş-Cătălin Barbu of ICI Bucharest	Adrian-Victor Vevera Dragoş-Cătălin Barbu	ICI Bucuresti	Romania	RH East
Bottom-up meets top-down: Hungary’s formula for building Open Science communities	Ildikó Kádárné Kelemen János Mohácsi	KIFÜ	Hungary	RH Central

Title	Interviewee	MO Name	Country	Regional Hub
Driving Open Science in Greece: Insights from Kostas Koumantaros of GRNET	Kostas Koumantaros	GRNET	Greece	RH South
Slovenia set to unlock the benefits of Open Science through the EOSC Federation	Peter Sterle Marko Bonač Marko Drobnjak	Arnes	Slovenia	RH Central
Open Science in Ukraine: Resilience and progress amid war	Sergiy Svistunov	Bogolyubov Institute for Theoretical Physics of the National Academy of Science of Ukraine	Ukraine	RH East
Open Science and the advancement of Latvia's research capabilities on a global scale	Jānis Grēviņš	VPC	Latvia	RH East
Building a sustainable Open Science infrastructure: Portugal's approach	João Mendes Moreira	FCT	Portugal	RH South